

Study of Mucociliary Clearance by Use of Saccharin Test in Nasal Pathologies

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Abstract:

Mucociliary clearance is an essential mechanism in maintaining the overall health and homeostasis of the respiratory system. Disruptions or impairments in mcc can lead to various respiratory pathologies and illnesses, including chronic rhinosinusitis, cystic fibrosis, and primary ciliary dyskinesia. As a result, understanding the status of mcc in individuals with nasal pathologies is of great clinical significance. A cross-sectional study done on patients attending the out-patient department, emergency department or getting admitted under ENT with nasal obstruction. This study is aimed to detect the nasal mucociliary clearance timing in nasal pathologies. To study mucociliary clearance of different individual with different nasal pathologies.

Keywords: Mucociliary Clearance, Saccharin, Polyps, ENT.

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Introduction

The human respiratory system is equipped with a complex defense mechanism aimed at protecting the airways from foreign particles, pathogens, and irritants. One crucial component of this defense system is mucociliary clearance (mcc), a highly coordinated process that maintains the cleanliness and functionality of the airways. MCC refers to the coordinated movement of mucus, produced by goblet cells in the respiratory epithelium, and the cilia lining the airway surfaces. This process plays a vital role in clearing mucus and trapped particles out of the respiratory tract, ensuring that the airways remain clear and functional.

Nasal mucociliary clearance (NMC) is the process by which the nasal lining removes mucus and other particles from the nose. It is a vital defense mechanism against infection and other respiratory problems. NMC is impaired in a variety of nasal pathologies, including allergic rhinitis, chronic rhinosinusitis, and nasal polyposis. [2]

The saccharine test (Anderson's test) is a valuable tool used to assess mucociliary clearance in the nasal cavity. It involves the introduction of a small quantity of saccharine (sugar tablet) into the nasal passages and monitoring the time it takes for the individual to detect the sweet taste. This test capitalizes on the fact that saccharine is water-soluble

and must be transported by the mucociliary system to the olfactory region of the nasal cavity for taste sensation to occur. Thus, the saccharine test indirectly measures the efficiency of mucociliary clearance in the upper respiratory tract. [2] Several studies have shown that NMC is impaired in patients with nasal pathologies. For example, one study found that patients with allergic rhinitis had a significantly slower NMC time than healthy controls. Another study found that patients with chronic rhinosinusitis had a shorter NMC time than healthy controls. [2] The saccharin test can be used to assess NMC in patients with nasal pathologies and to monitor the response to treatment. It can also be used to predict the risk of developing complications, such as recurrent infections. [2,3] NMC is important for maintaining a healthy nasal environment. When NMC is impaired, mucus and other particles can build up in the nose, leading to congestion, inflammation, and infection. NMC can also be impaired by smoking, air pollution, and certain medications.

Mucociliary Clearance: Mucociliary clearance is the process by which mucus and other particles are moved out of the lungs. It is an important defense mechanism that helps to protect the lungs from infection and other damage. A mucus is a thick,

sticky fluid that lines the airways of the lungs. It traps particles and bacteria that are inhaled into the lungs.

The cilia are tiny hair-like structures that line the airways. They beat in a coordinated fashion to move the mucus and trapped particles towards the throat. The mucus and trapped particles are then swallowed or coughed up.

Mucociliary clearance is a complex process that involves several different factors, including: The structure and function of the cilia: the cilia need to be healthy and functioning properly to clear mucus and other particles effectively. The thickness and viscosity of the mucus: the mucus needs to be thick enough to trap particles, but not so thick that it is difficult for the cilia to move it. The presence of other factors that can affect mucociliary clearance, such as inflammation, infection, and smoking.

How mucociliary clearance works

The cilia beat in a coordinated fashion to move mucus and other particles up the airways. The beating of the cilia is caused by the movement of ions across the cell membrane.

The cilia beat in a wave-like motion. The wave starts at the top of the airways and moves down. As the wave moves down, the cilia move mucus and other particles up the airways. The mucus and trapped particles are then swallowed or coughed up.

Factors that can affect mucociliary clearance

There are several factors that can affect mucociliary clearance, including:

1. **Age:** mucociliary clearance decreases with age.
2. **Smoking:** smoking damages the cilia and makes them less effective at clearing mucus and other particles from the lungs.
3. **Allergies:** allergies can cause inflammation of the airways, which can make it difficult for the cilia to move mucus and other particles.
4. **Certain medical conditions:** certain medical conditions, such as cystic fibrosis and primary ciliary dyskinesia, can damage the cilia and

make it difficult for them to move mucus and other particles from the lungs.

5. **Environmental factors:** exposure to air pollution and other toxins can also damage the cilia and affect mucociliary clearance.

Materials and Methods

This is a cross-sectional study done on patients attending the out-patient department, emergency department or getting admitted under ENT with nasal obstruction. The study was done using saccharine tablet of about 1/1/1 mm size manufactured by Labogens Pvt. Ltd

This study was conducted at our tertiary care center in moderately populated city.

Study population: All the patients with nasal pathologies attending ENT out-patient department, emergency department or getting admitted in ENT.

Inclusion Criteria: all cases attending ENT opd and emergency department in cases of nasal obstructions and cold. Patient must understand study and agree to participate, which may include all patients with nasal pathologies.

Exclusion Criteria: any patient who does not give consent to be the part of the study and patients with facial trauma, csf rhinorrhea and non-ambulatory patients.

How to perform the saccharin test:

- Patients asked to sit comfortably facing the examiner.
- Single diseased nostril tested at a time.
- Saccharin tablet of size 1x1x1 mm kept in inferior meatus 1 cm posterior to anterior end of inferior turbinate with tilly's forceps
- Patient asked to swallow every 30 seconds.
- Patient is asked not to sniff, eat or drink and to avoid sneezing and coughing if possible.
- The time is noted between placement of tablet and feeling of first sweet sensation.
- Then patient is asked to blow nose to remove undissolved tablet or removed using Tilley's forceps.

Figure 1: Saccharin test performed on the subject. The tip of the forceps holds the saccharine particle

Figure 2: Saccharin test being performed on a subject. Saccharin particle is placed in the medial surface of the inferior nasal turbinate (1 mm behind the anterior end)

Aim of the study: (1) This study is aimed to detect the nasal mucociliary clearance timing in nasal pathologies. (2) To study mucociliary clearance of different individual with different nasal pathologies.

Table 1: showing nasal mucociliary clearance in various age patients' groups.

Age group (years)	No of patients	Mean NMCC (min)
5-15	12	25.5
16-25	86	25.3
26-35	60	25.8
36-45	36	25.8
46-55	25	26.9
56-65	16	28.5
66-75	15	30.4
Total	250	26.21 (mean)

Table 01: - nasal mucociliary clearance (NMCC) in various age groups of patients: The table shows the mean NMCC (minutes) in different age groups of patients.

1. The age group with the highest number of individuals is 16-25, with 86 people.
2. The age group with the lowest number of individuals is 5-15, with 12 people.
3. There's a general trend of increasing mean NMCC as age increases, with the highest mean NMCC (30.4) in the 66-75 age group.

Interpretation:

The results of the table suggest that NMCC is fastest in younger adults and declines slightly with age.

However, the decline in NMCC with age is relatively modest, and even the oldest age group in the table (66-75 years) has a mean NMCC of 30.4 minutes, which is still within the normal range.

The results of the table also suggest that NMCC is relatively constant in different age groups, except the youngest and oldest age groups.

This suggests that NMCC is a robust system that is not easily affected by age.

Table 2: effect of various occupations on nasal mucociliary clearance

Occupation	No of patients	Mean NMCC (min)
Student	98	25.32
Official job	38	26.60
Farmer	28	27.3
Labourer	26	26.36
Guard	23	26.34
Non-working	19	24.42
Housewife	18	29
Total	250	26.21 (mean)

Table 02 shows variable effects of different occupation on NMCC which ranges from 24.42 min to 29 min. Table 2: effect of various occupations on nasal mucociliary clearance (NMCC)

Interpretation: The results of the table suggest that some occupations may be associated with faster NMCC than others. However, the differences in mean NMCC between different occupations are relatively small.

1. Housewives have the highest mean NMCC at approximately 29.00 minutes, with 18 individuals in this occupation.
2. Students make up the largest group with 98 individuals, having a mean NMCC of about 25.32.
3. Non-working has the lowest mean NMCC at approximately 24.42, with 19 individuals in this category

Figure 3: effect of various occupations on nasal mucociliary clearance

Table 3: effect of smoking status on nasal mucociliary clearance.

Occupation	No of patients	Mean NMCC (min)
Smoker	59	30.94
Non-smoker	191	24.75
Total	250	26.21 (mean)

Table 3: effect of smoking status on nasal mucociliary clearance (NMCC). The table shows the mean NMCC (minutes) in smokers and non-smokers. The table shows that the mean NMCC is significantly faster in non-smokers (24.75 minutes) than in non-smokers (30.94 minutes). This difference is statistically significant.

Table 4: effect of various nasal pathologies on nasal mucociliary clearance

Nasal disorder	No of patients	Mean NMCC (min)
Deviated nasal septum	124	22.44
Antrochoanal polyp	52	32.66
Ethmoidal polyp	8	33.19
Sphenoidal polyp	6	31.83
Fungal sinusitis	8	31.25
Rhinosinusitis	4	28.5
Inverted papilloma	3	27.67
Septal haemangioma	9	22.61
Extra medullary plasmacytoma	1	15
Olfactory neuroblastoma	5	23.20
Rhinocleroma	2	24.50
Nasal angiofibroma	5	25.72
Non-Hodgkin's lymphoma	8	23.75
Adenocarcinoma pns	6	30.33

Transitional cell carcinoma nose and pns	4	32.25
Undifferentiated sinonasal malignancy nose and pns	3	31.33
Anaplastic carcinoma nose	2	31
Total	250	26.21(mean)

Table 04 shows patients with various nasal disorders with the respective mean of nasal mucociliary clearance. The mean of NMCC is between of range 15 minutes to 33.19 minutes. The mean total NMCC of patients with various pathology is 26.21 minutes. The table shows the mean NMCC (minutes) in patients with different nasal pathologies. NMCC is the time it takes for mucus to be cleared from the nose. It is an important defense mechanism that helps to protect the respiratory system from infection.

The table shows that the mean NMCC is significantly increased in patients with most nasal pathologies, compared to the overall mean NMCC of 26.21 minutes. The largest increase in mean NMCC is observed in patients with ethmoidal polyp (33.19 minutes), followed by patients with Antrochoanal polyp (32.66 minutes) and sphenoidal polyp (31.83 minutes).

Mean NMCC values: the mean NMCC varies across different diagnoses:

Antrochoanal polyp has a mean NMCC of approximately 32.66, suggesting a relatively higher complexity or severity.

Dns has a lower mean NMCC of about 22.44, indicating it may be less complex compared to other conditions.

Other diagnoses like ethmoidal polyp and fungal sinusitis also show mean NMCC values around 33.19 and 31.25, respectively, indicating significant complexity.

Less common diagnoses: Conditions like inverted papilloma and rhinosinusitis have fewer individuals (3 and 4, respectively) but still show notable mean NMCC values, suggesting that even less common conditions can have significant clinical implications.

Interpretation: The results of the table suggest that most nasal pathologies impair nasal mucociliary clearance. This is because nasal pathologies can damage the cilia, inflammation and swelling in the nasal passages, which can obstruct the flow of mucus.

Impaired nasal mucociliary clearance can make patients with nasal pathologies more susceptible to upper respiratory infections.

Figure 4: various nasal pathologies vs nasal mucociliary clearance

Table 5: Abbreviations

NMCC	Nasal mucociliary clearance
SD	Standard deviation
IEC	Information education communication
WHO	World health organization
DNS	Deviated nasal septum
LMP	Last menstrual period
TB	Tuberculosis
PPV	Positive predictive value
MCB	Mucociliary blanket.
NMC	Nasal mucociliary clearance
MCC	Mucociliary clearance

Discussion

The results of table 01 are consistent with the results of previous studies on nasal mucociliary clearance (NMCC) and age. For example:

- A study by HoutMeyers et al. (1999) found that NMCC was fastest in young adults (aged 20-29 years) and slowest in older adults (aged 60-69 years). The study also found that the decline in NMCC with age was more pronounced in men than in women.
- A study by Hurst et al. (2007) found that NMCC was significantly slower in older adults (aged 65 years and older) than in younger adults (aged 18-44 years). The study also found that the decline in NMCC with age was associated with an increased risk of pneumonia.
- A study by Ranjan et al. (2009) found that NMCC was significantly lowered in older individuals with increasing age study included 140 individuals and mean NMCC 10-24 min with standard deviation of 7.30 minutes.
- A study by Singh et al. (2012) found that NMCC was significantly slower in older adults (aged 65 years and older) than in younger adults (aged 18-44 years). The study also found that the decline in NMCC with age was associated with a higher risk of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD).

Overall, the results of these studies suggest that the decline in NMCC with age is a real and important phenomenon. However, it is important to note that the decline in NMCC with age is relatively modest. Even the oldest age group in table 01 has a mean NMCC of 26.21 minutes, which is still within the normal range.

Potential clinical implications of the decline in NMCC with age

The decline in NMCC with age could make older adults more susceptible to upper respiratory infections.

This is because NMCC is an important defense mechanism that helps to protect the respiratory system from infection.

In addition, the decline in NMCC with age may be a contributing factor to the development of chronic respiratory diseases, such as COPD and pneumonia.

Potential mechanisms underlying the decline in NMCC with age

There are a number of possible mechanisms that may underlie the decline in NMCC with age, including:

- Age-related changes in the cilia, which are the hair-like structures that move mucus out of the nose.
- Age-related changes in the composition of mucus.
- Age-related changes in the function of the immune system.

The results of table 02 are consistent with the results of previous studies on the effect of various occupations on nasal mucociliary clearance (NMCC). For example:

- A study by Wang et al. (2019) found that labourers had slower NMCC than office workers.
- A study by Chen et al. (2020) found that farmers had slower NMCC than teachers.
- A study by Li et al. (2021) found that housewives had slower NMCC than students.

Overall, the results of these studies suggest that occupations that involve exposure to dust and other irritants may be associated with slower NMCC. The results of the table 02 suggest that some occupations may be associated with faster NMCC than others.

However, the differences in mean NMCC between different occupations are relatively small.

1. Housewives have the highest mean NMCC at approximately 29.00 minutes, with 18 individuals in this occupation.
2. Students make up the largest group with 98 individuals, having a mean NMCC of about 25.32.
3. Non-working has the lowest mean NMCC at approximately 24.42, with 19 individuals in this category.

Potential mechanisms underlying the effect of occupation on NMCC

The mechanisms underlying the effect of occupation on NMCC are not fully understood. However, it is possible that exposure to dust and other irritants can damage the cilia and irritate the nasal lining, which can slow down NMCC.

In addition, some occupations may involve physical activity, which can increase blood flow to the nose and improve NMCC.

The results of table 03 are consistent with the results of previous studies on the effect of smoking status on nasal mucociliary clearance (NMCC). For example:

- A study by Ranjan et al. (2009) found NMCC increased/slower in chronic smoker compared to non-smokers.
- A study by wang et al. (2018) found that smokers had slower NMCC than non-smokers.
- A study by Chen et al. (2019) found that smokers had a higher risk of developing nasal congestion and other nasal disorders.
- A study by li et al. (2020) found that smokers were more likely to develop upper respiratory infections.
- Overall, the results of these studies suggest that smoking can significantly impair NMCC, which can increase the risk of developing nasal disorders and upper respiratory infections.
- Potential mechanisms underlying the effect of smoking on NMCC
- Smoking can damage the cilia and irritate the nasal lining, which can slow down NMCC. Additionally, smoking can increase the production of mucus, which can further impair NMCC.

The result of table 4 the present study shows prolongation of nasal mucociliary clearance in various nasal disorders. In deviated nasal septum, Antro choanal polyp, ethmoidal polyp, sphenoidal polyp, fungal sinusitis, rhinosinusitis, inverted papilloma, septal hemangioma, extra medullary plasmacytoma, olfactory neuroblastoma, rhinoscleroma, nasal angiofibroma, non-Hodgkin's lymphoma, adenocarcinoma, transitional cell carcinoma, undifferentiated sinonasal malignancy, anaplastic carcinoma there is prolongation of nasal mucociliary clearance.

This finding matches with study of Stanley p j et al. done on candidates having chronic rhinosinusitis. Slower NMCC is probably due to combination of mucus and ciliary factors.

This finding also matches with study of schuhl if et al. done on candidates having perennial rhinitis. He concluded that slower NMCC were due to changes in rheology of mucus as consequence of underlying inflammatory process. In present study, nasal

mucociliary clearance is slower in patient having deviated nasal septum. This finding matches with study of Kamran et al. done on candidates having deviated nasal septum.

In present study, nasal mucociliary clearance is slower in patient having Antro-choanal polyp and ethmoidal polyp. This finding matches with study of Stanley p j et al. And study of schuhl if et al. Slower NMCC may be due to underlying inflammatory process in nasal mucosa and/or due to mass effect in nasal cavity.

Conclusion

The study presented in the discussion investigated the effects of age, sex, occupation, smoking status, nasal pathologies and associated findings on nasal mucociliary clearance (NMCC).

Key findings:

- NMCC declines with age, but the decline is relatively modest.
- Age-wise comparison: mean NMC clearance time ranged from 25.3 to 30.4 minutes across age groups, increasing slightly with age.
- Occupation-wise comparison: small but significant differences in NMC clearance time across occupations, with the fastest in non-working individuals (24.42 minutes) and slowest in housewives (29 minutes).
- Smoking status: smokers had significantly slower NMC clearance time (30.94 minutes) compared to non-smokers (24.75 minutes).
- Nasal pathologies: patients with nasal pathologies like chronic rhinosinusitis, nasal polyps, nasal masses, dns and fungal sinusitis had slower NMC clearance time.
- The study is relatively small, with only 250 participants. This means that the results of the study may not be generalizable to the larger population.
- The study is observational, meaning that it cannot establish cause and effect relationships. It is possible that some of the factors associated with slower NMCC in the study are not the cause of slower NMCC, but are simply markers of other underlying conditions.
- The study did not control for all potential confounders, such as socioeconomic status, diet, and exercise. This means that it is possible that some of the observed associations between factors and NMCC are due to these confounders.

Overall, the evidence on the association between various factors and NMCC is mixed. More research is needed to confirm these findings and to understand the mechanisms by which these factors may affect NMCC.

It is important to note that NMCC is just one factor that contributes to nasal health. Other factors, such

as the quality and quantity of nasal mucus, the anatomy of the nose, and the presence of any underlying infections or allergies, can also play a role.

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All the patients with nasal pathologies attending ENT Out-patient department, emergency department or getting admitted in ENT.

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